

EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE WORKPLACE: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

This study aims to map empirical findings on employee engagement as a dependent variable in workplace contexts using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach. Literature searches were conducted across three academic databases: Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and Garuda Ristekdikti, covering publications from 2020 to 2025. Article selection followed PRISMA guidelines, with inclusion criteria comprising quantitative studies, workplace-focused contexts, employee engagement as the dependent variable, and full-text accessibility in Indonesian or English. Out of 395,874 identified records, 24 articles met all inclusion criteria and were further analyzed. Findings were synthesized using meta-analytic techniques where applicable and complemented by narrative synthesis to interpret heterogeneous results. The review indicates that organizational factors such as leadership styles, human resource management practices, perceived organizational support, quality of work life, and workplace environment have a significant effect on employee engagement. Individual and contextual factors, including workplace spirituality and employee well-being, also have an effect on enhancing engagement. This review highlights research gaps, particularly the limited evidence from Indonesian MSMEs and the underexplored role of several predictors, thereby offering directions for future research.

Keywords: *employee engagement, systematic literature review, organizational factors, workplace*

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, employee engagement has become one of the central constructs in industrial and organizational psychology and human resource management. Employee engagement is understood as a condition in which employees actively direct their physical, cognitive, and emotional energy into their work roles and organizational activities (Kahn, 1990). A high level of employee engagement has been proven to correlate with various positive outcomes, such as improved performance, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and reduced turnover intention (Bakker and Demerouti, 2008; Saks, 2006). In the context of modern organizations facing dynamic change, digitalization, economic uncertainty, and increasingly complex job demands, efforts to maintain employee engagement have become a strategic challenge for organizations. The Job Demands Resources model explains that employee engagement is influenced by the balance between job demands and job resources, such as supervisor support, autonomy, and development opportunities (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). A number of empirical studies show that organizational factors such as leadership style, job satisfaction, organizational support, and quality of work environment have a significant effect on employee engagement (He et al., 2021; Nguyen and Tran, 2021; Rasool et al., 2021; Asefa and Kant, 2022; Luthfi and Putri, 2021; Shi et al., 2025).

Although research on employee engagement continues to develop, existing findings show variation in context, theoretical approaches, and predictor variables used. Some studies emphasize the role of organizational factors, such as transformational leadership, human resource management practices, and organizational support, while other studies highlight the role of individual and contextual factors, such as employee well being, workplace spirituality, and person organization fit. This variation, on the one hand, enriches the understanding of the determinants of employee engagement; however, on the other hand, it makes it difficult to draw comprehensive conclusions regarding which factors most consistently and contextually enhance employee engagement, particularly in the most recent research period. In addition, most previous studies still focus on corporate sectors or large organizations in developed countries, while empirical evidence in the context of developing countries, including Indonesia, and in the MSME sector remains relatively limited. In fact, organizational characteristics, work culture, and resource limitations in MSMEs may have an effect on the dynamics of employee engagement differently

compared to large organizations. Therefore, a systematic mapping of recent empirical findings is needed to identify general patterns, research gaps, and opportunities for future research development. Based on this background, this study aims to conduct a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) of empirical studies that position employee engagement as a dependent variable in workplace contexts during the period 2020 to 2025. Through this approach, this study is expected to (1) map the characteristics of the population and research context of employee engagement, (2) identify organizational, individual, and contextual factors that have an effect on employee engagement, (3) evaluate the methodological strengths and limitations of previous studies, and (4) formulate recommendations for future research directions that are theoretically and practically relevant.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee engagement has become a central construct in human resource management research due to its critical role in enhancing individual and organizational performance. Kahn (1990) conceptualized engagement as a psychological condition in which employees express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally in their work roles, while Bakker and Demerouti (2008) described it as a positive work-related state characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Saks (2006) further emphasized that employee engagement is shaped by organizational and individual factors and leads to important outcomes such as commitment and job performance. Leadership and human resource management practices have been consistently identified as key determinants of employee engagement. Balwant et al. (2019) found that transformational leadership enhances engagement through job resources, whereas Asefa and Kant (2022) demonstrated that transactional academic leadership influences engagement via extrinsic motivation. Similar findings were reported by He et al. (2021), Jing and Nuruly (2025), and Rumman et al. (2020), who highlighted the roles of high-performance HR practices, human resource development, and leader–member exchange in fostering employee engagement.

Beyond structural factors, psychosocial aspects and the work environment significantly contribute to employee engagement. Rasool et al. (2021) and Cherlyn and Sentoso (2022) showed that toxic workplace environments reduce engagement through employee well-being and organizational support, while Nguyen and Tran (2021) emphasized the importance of perceived organizational support, particularly during crisis periods. Okojie et al. (2024) further noted that social support mediates the relationship between individual traits and engagement, whereas Na-Nan et al. (2025) highlighted the mediating role of psychological contracts in the relationship between person–organization fit and employee engagement. Workplace spirituality has also emerged as an important predictor of employee engagement. Studies by Mutiara and Nurhayati (2023), Purnami et al. (2020), Nufus and Mubarak (2022), and Okfrima et al. (2022) consistently reported positive effects of workplace spirituality on engagement, either directly or indirectly through achievement motivation and knowledge sharing. Supporting these findings, Agustiani et al. (2024) demonstrated that workplace happiness enhances employee engagement through the mediating role of quality of work life, underscoring the importance of psychological well-being in contemporary workplaces.

Furthermore, individual and demographic characteristics influence variations in employee engagement. Lartey (2021) identified career planning, employee autonomy, and managerial recognition as significant contributors, while Shi et al. (2025) showed that perceived vulnerability to disease affects employees' engagement levels. Ramirez Lozano et al. (2023) also emphasized the roles of leadership, communication, and job satisfaction in sustaining employee engagement, particularly within family business contexts. Overall, the literature indicates that employee engagement is a multidimensional construct shaped by leadership, HR practices, work environment, organizational support, workplace spirituality, and individual characteristics. Despite extensive empirical evidence, there remains a need for integrative studies that simultaneously examine psychological, organizational, and contextual factors, particularly within specific sectors and regional settings, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms underlying employee engagement.

METHOD

This study uses a Systematic Literature Review approach to identify, evaluate, and synthesize empirical findings related to factors that have an effect on employee engagement as a dependent variable in workplace contexts. The Systematic Literature Review approach was selected because it is able to provide a comprehensive and systematic overview of research development, patterns of findings, and research gaps that remain open as a basis for formulating recommendations for future research. As a structured method, the Systematic Literature Review emphasizes limiting bias in the process of searching, selecting, and synthesizing studies, and complies with specific scientific protocols such as PRISMA Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses as a

reference in conducting the initial literature selection (Liberati et al., 2009). In addition, the Systematic Literature Review aims to map the characteristics of previous studies, including the population examined, the theoretical framework used, and the methodological approach applied.

1. Literature Search Procedure

The literature search procedure in this study was conducted systematically to ensure broad coverage while maintaining relevance to the research focus. The search strategy was based on the principles of traceability and transparency in identifying articles that examine employee engagement as a dependent variable in workplace contexts. Literature sources were obtained from three academic databases, namely Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and Garuda Ristekdikti. The selection of these three databases was based on their broad literature coverage, accessibility, and relevance in providing national and international scientific articles that have undergone a peer review process and are related to employee engagement in workplace contexts. In addition, the selection of literature also considered reputation, accessibility, and relevance to the fields of organizational psychology and management. The search process included an initial screening stage, elimination of irrelevant articles, and final selection of articles that met the inclusion criteria. These criteria were determined based on the alignment of the topic with the research focus, namely employee engagement as a dependent variable, full text accessibility, and clarity in the use of employee engagement measurement instruments as the primary focus of analysis. This selection process resulted in a collection of articles that formed the basis of analysis in this study and was conducted in accordance with general principles of systematic review, including transparency in the selection stages and documentation of the search and screening flow of the literature.

2. Research Stage

a. Identification Stage

At this stage, the initial research process was conducted by sorting relevant articles using specific keywords. The keywords used included “employee engagement”, “employee engagement as an outcome”, and “employee engagement in workplace”. These keywords were combined using Boolean operators such as AND, OR, and NOT. This process aimed to collect articles relevant to the research topic within a specific time range 2015 to 2025, after which several sources were further filtered to the period 2020 to 2025. Alternatively, articles with high relevance in terms of topic and methodology published in earlier years were also considered. In addition, the search was conducted using filters based on publication type, such as scientific journals or proceedings containing empirical or theoretical data related to employee engagement as a dependent variable.

b. Coding and Filtering Stage

The coding and filtering stage in this study was conducted using a rigorous and systematic approach in accordance with the Systematic Literature Review method to ensure that only relevant and high quality studies were analyzed. The screening process was carried out based on predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria, in which eligible studies had to specifically examine employee engagement as a dependent variable, use a quantitative research design, and demonstrate data collection techniques as well as the validity and reliability of the variables (Moher et al., 2009). The selection process began with reading the titles and abstracts to eliminate irrelevant articles, followed by full text review of articles that met the initial criteria. This aimed to verify the relevance and feasibility of the data to be analyzed so that selection bias could be minimized (Peters et al., 2015).

c. Analysis Stage

At the analysis stage, the coded data were synthesized using meta analysis techniques, allowing statistical integration from multiple studies to assess the combined effect on the employee engagement variable (Borenstein et al., 2009). The analysis was also supported by a narrative approach to discuss specific aspects when quantitative data were insufficient or unavailable. This Systematic Literature Review emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive and critical evaluation of employee engagement as a dependent variable, including discussion of the factors that have an effect on it (Mokkink et al., 2010). Thus, the mapping of findings can indicate gaps in the existing literature as well as directions for future research related to the development and refinement of related variables (Liberati et al., 2009).

3. Research Question

The Research Question is structured based on the PICO framework related to the discussion of the articles to be analyzed:

Component	Description
P (Population)	Employees in various types of workplaces
I (Intervention)	Leadership style, communication, environment, organizational support, employee well being, family support, quality of work life QoWL, individual spirituality, toxic workplace environment, workplace spirituality, Human Resource Management HRM, trait engagement, psychological contract, person organization fit
C (Comparison)	The number of intensity of the use of each variable
O (Outcome)	Factors that have not been widely examined as independent variables on employee engagement recommendations for future research

RQ1: Who are the employee populations examined in studies on employee engagement during the period 2020 to 2025?

RQ2: What organizational factors have been proven effective in enhancing employee engagement in the workplace based on empirical studies in the last five years?

RQ3: What are the strengths and limitations of each article reviewed in terms of population, theoretical framework, and research method?

RQ4: What factors are recommended for further research in terms of factors that have not been widely examined and the strengths and limitations of the theoretical framework and research method.

4. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Aspect	Inclusion Criteria
Research context	Studies focusing on workplace contexts
Research topic	Employee engagement as a dependent variable
Publication year range	Articles published between 2020 and 2025
Research type	Quantitative studies
Article language	Articles written in Indonesian or English

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Article Search Results

Based on the Systematic Literature Review diagram presented in the figure, the process from identification to included articles consisted of three main stages, namely identification, screening, and included. At the initial stage, articles were searched using the keyword “employee engagement” in three databases. From Google Scholar, 389,002 articles were identified; from ScienceDirect, 4,685 articles; and from Garuda Ristekdikti, 2,186 articles. The total number of identified articles was 395,873. An initial filtering process was then conducted to exclude articles that did not focus on workplace contexts. A total of 121,917 articles were not relevant to workplace contexts.

After the identification stage, a screening process was conducted on the remaining articles. The number of screened articles was 273,957. The next stage involved applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria included publication year, research type, language, open access availability, and topic relevance. Articles published outside the 2020 to 2025 period totaled 273,774, and five articles used a qualitative research design. The remaining 176 articles met the inclusion criteria. A title and abstract screening was then conducted on these 176 articles. At the final stage, a full selection process was carried out to ensure that the included articles were open access and did not merely focus on a dependent variable without direct relevance to employee engagement as the main variable. A total of 125 articles were not available as open access, and 27 articles had a dependent variable focus that was not aligned with the research objective; therefore, they were excluded from the analysis. From the entire process, 24 articles met all inclusion criteria and were further analyzed in this review.

2. Analysis of Articles Included in the Systematic Review

The following table summarizes the articles to facilitate the identification and comprehensive understanding of the studies analyzed in this review.

No	Writer	Article Title	Population	IV (factor) -> DV
1.	1. Julianna Ramirez Lozano, 2. Renato PeñaflorGuerra, 3. Victoria SanagustínFons	Leadership, Communication, and Job Satisfaction for Employee Engagement and Sustainability of Family Businesses in Latin America	Employees in two family businesses and MSMEs in Peru	1. Participative leadership style 2. Effective communication 3. Job satisfaction
2.	1. Paul Tristen Balwant, 2. Rehaana Mohammed, 3. Riann Singh	Transformational Leadership and Employee Engagement in Trinidad’s Service Sector: The Role of Job Resources	Retail store employees in 10 shopping centers in Trinidad	1. Transformational leadership 2. Job resources
3.	1. Jie He, 2. Alastair M.Morrison, 3. HaoZhang	How High Performance HR Practices and LMX Affect Employee Engagement and Creativity in Hospitality	hotel employees in China	1. HR performance 2. Leader-Member Exchange (LMX)
4.	1. Samma FaizRasool, 2. MansiWang, 3. MinzeTang, 4. AmirSaeed, 5. JavedIqbal	How Toxic Workplace Environment Effects the Employee Engagement: The Mediating Role of Organizational Support and Employee Wellbeing	Employees in Chinese SMEs	1. Toxic workplace environment (TWE) 2. Organizational support 3. Employee wellbeing

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5.	Franklin M. Lartey	Impact of Career Planning, Employee Autonomy, and Manager Recognition on Employee Engagement	SME employees in the US	1. Career planning 2. Manager recognition 3. Employee autonomy
6.	1. Nguyen Hai Ninh, 2. Tran Manh Dung	The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Engagement During the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Empirical Study in Vietnam	Corporate office employees in Hanoi, Vietnam	1. Perceived organizational support 2. Perceived family support
7.	1. Poppy Sofia Koeswoyo, 2. Haryanto Haryanto, 3. Sofik Handoyo	The impact of corporate governance, internal control and corporate reputation on employee engagement: a moderating role of leadership style	Not explicitly stated, but suspected to involve mid-to-upper level employees or managers	1. Corporate governance 2. Internal control 3. Corporate reputation 4. Leadership style
8.	1. Amani Abu Rumman, 2. LinaAlAbbadi, 3. Rawan Alshawabkeh	The impact of human resource development practices on employee engagement and performance in Jordanian family restaurants	employee of a family restaurant in Amman, Jordan	HRD (empowerment and promotion)
9.	1. Kebede Asefa Debelo, 2. Shashi Kant	Transactional Academic Leadership Effect on Employee's Engagement: The Mediating Impact of Extrinsic Motivation	academic staff of higher education institutions in Ethiopia	Extrinsic Motivation
10.	1. Mappamiring Mappamiring, 2. Aditya Halim Perdana Kusuma Putra	Understanding Career Optimism on Employee Engagement: Broaden Built and Organizational Theory Perspective	lecturers from universities in Indonesia	1. Career optimism 2. Organizational fairness 3. Organizational entrepreneurial commitment
11.	1. Tengku Wildan Luthfi, 2. Vini Wiratno Putri	Factors That Affect Employee Engagement in the Workplace	Employees of PT. BPR Surya Yudhakencana, Banjarnegara Head Office	1. Servant leadership 2. Job satisfaction
12.	1. Titin Agustiani, 2. Linda Mora, 3. Choirul Ibad	Increasing Employee Engagement Through Workplace Happiness: A Quality of Work Life Mediation Study	employees of PT Pupuk Kujang	1. Quality of work life (QoWL) 2. Worklife happiness
13.	1. Rahayu Sri Purnami, 2. Syamsul Hadi Monday, 3. Disman Disman, 4. Eeng Ahman	The Influence of Individual Spirituality and Workplace Spirituality on Employee Engagement of Digital Marketing Agency Employees	Digital marketing agency employees (mostly millennials)	1. Individual spirituality 2. Workplace spirituality
14.	1. Ria Okfrima, 2. Budi Harto, 3. M.Asbullah, 4. Nila Pratiwi,	Relationship Between Workplace Spirituality and Employee Engagement in the Milling Sector of PT. Family Raya	employees in the milling sector of PT. Family Raya Padang	Workplace spirituality

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	5. Marina Lestari Pasaribu			
15.	1. Rahma Zakiyyatun Nufus, 2. Ali Mubarak	Study of the contribution of workplace spirituality to employee engagement of Bandung City firefighters	Firefighters in Bandung City	Workplace spirituality
16.	1. Cherlyn, 2. Antony Sentoso	The Effect of Toxic Workplace Environment Mediated by Organizational Culture, Work Environment, Organizational Support and Employee WellBeing on Employee Engagement in the Hospitality	Hotel employees in Batam City	1. Toxic workplace environment 2. Organizational culture 3. work environment 4. organizational support 5. Employee well-being
17.	1. ZhaoJing, 2. SantiNuruly	The Impact of Human Resource Management on Employee Engagement in Workplace of Primostar, Shanghai	Primostar Employees, Shanghai	Human Resource Management
18.	1. Meyvanali, 2. Della Edelweiss Manalu, 3. Rahel Gabriel Rosabeth Sibatuara	Workplace Environment's Impact on Employee Engagement: Social Cognitive Perspective	Not explicitly stated, but generally in the form of employees in an organization or company, possibly taken from one or several organizations.	Workplace environment
19.	1. Athiyah Nadiya Rianti Mutiara, 2. Mafizatun Nurhayati	Workplace Spirituality and Knowledge Sharing on Employee Engagement: Mediated Role by Achievement Motivation	Permanent teacher at an educational foundation in West Jakarta	1. Workplace spirituality 2. Achievement motivation
20.	1. Jian Shi, 2. Alexandra (Sasha) Cook, 3. Mark van Vugt, 4. Arnold B. Bakker	Do Individual Differences in Perceived Vulnerability to Disease Shape Employees' Work Engagement?	Adult employees working in the UK	1. Individual perception 2. Health-Oriented Leadership
21.	1. Glory Okojie, 2. ASA Ferdous Alam, 3. Halima Begum, 4. Ida Rosnita Ismail, 5. Elkhan Richard Sadik-Zada	Social Support as a Mediator Between Selected Trait Engagement and Employee Engagement	Registered nurse working in a public hospital in Lagos, Nigeria	Trait engagement
22.	1. Khan Na-Nan, 2. Kanakarn Phanniphong, 3. Nutt Jaturat,	The Influence of Person-Organization Fit on Employee Engagement: Psychological Contract as a Mediating Effect	Employees in Thailand's logistics industry	1. Person-Organizational Fit 2. Psychological contract

	4. Natnarong Jaturat, 5. Malee Jaturat	in Thailand's Logistics Industry		
23.	1. GKT Manjula, 2. E. Rebecca	The Impact of Toxic Workplace Environment on Employee Engagement: The Mediating Role of Jpb Anxiety in ABC Copany of Sri Lanka	Employees in Sri Lankan corporations	1. Toxic Workplace Environment 2. Job anxiety
24.	1. Willy Tambunan, 2. Sri Gunani Partiwī, 3. Adithya Sudiarno	Impact of toxic work environment on employee engagement mediated by employee well-being and supportive work culture	Mining industry employees in Indonesia	1. Toxic Workplace Environment 2. Employee Well-Being 3. Supportive Work Culture

3. Discussion of Main Findings Based on Research Questions RQ1, RQ2, RQ3, RQ4

RQ1: Who are the employee populations examined in studies on employee engagement during the period 2020 to 2025? This question refers to the professions of employees involved and the sectors in which they work. From the 22 articles analyzed, the populations were predominantly employees of state owned enterprises and manufacturing and service companies. Several studies also involved employees in educational institutions, such as lecturers, teachers, and academic staff. Populations in sectors such as healthcare, digital marketing agencies, firefighters, and logistics employees were also examined, although they were minimally represented. While several articles included populations from the MSME sector in various countries, none of the 22 analyzed articles examined MSME employees in Indonesia..

RQ2: What organizational factors have been proven effective in enhancing employee engagement in the workplace based on empirical studies in the last five years? This question refers to the most effective factors, which may be relational or structural depending on the organizational sector examined. The most frequently recurring organizational factors include leadership style transactional, servant, and participative, Human Resource Management practices training, career planning, and appraisal, and perceived organizational support. Organizational culture and workplace environment were also examined several times and were shown to have a direct effect on employee engagement. In addition, from the perspective of religiosity, workplace spirituality was frequently examined in several of the analyzed articles. Other factors that have a direct effect on employee engagement but were examined only once or twice include communication, job resources, individual spirituality, individual perception, trait engagement, and person organization fit.

RQ3: What are the strengths and limitations of each article reviewed in terms of population, theoretical framework, and research method?

The review of 22 scientific articles on employee engagement indicates that research approaches vary considerably in terms of population, theoretical framework, and research method. To address this question comprehensively, a sub research question is required, namely: How is employee engagement affected by individual, contextual, and organizational factors across various sectors and organizational cultures? Most articles used populations aligned with the research objectives. For example, Ramirez Lozano, Peñafior Guerra, and Sanagustín Fons 2023 and Rumman and Al Abbadi 2020 focused on MSMEs and family businesses in developing countries. Shi et al. 2025 explored engagement dynamics in an evolutionary and health crisis context. The strength of these studies lies in their ability to provide contextual local insights. However, several studies used non representative sampling techniques such as convenience sampling, had small sample sizes Okfrima et al. 2022; Nufus and Mubarak 2022, or did not clearly report population details Koeswoyo, Haryanto, and Handoyo 2024, thereby limiting generalizability. Articles integrating more than one theory tended to provide a more comprehensive explanation of engagement mechanisms. For instance, He et al. 2021 integrated AMO theory, Leader Member Exchange theory, and Self Determination Theory. Mappamiring and Putra 2021 combined Broaden and Build Theory and Organizational Theory to explain career optimism as a mediating variable. In contrast, several articles relied on a single theory or direct correlation models without examining mediation or moderation Okfrima et al. 2022; Luthfi and Putri 2021.

Most studies employed quantitative methods such as Structural Equation Modeling, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling, and regression analysis. Some studies, such as Ramirez Lozano, Peñaflores Guerra, and Sanagustín Fons 2023, combined quantitative and qualitative approaches. These approaches strengthen validity and analytical depth. However, some studies were limited to simple correlational approaches Okfrima et al. 2022 or did not report instrument validity in detail Rasool et al. 2021; Meyvanali, Manalu, and Sibatuara 2024.

Based on the findings, key factors of employee engagement include:

1. Individual factors: career optimism, personality traits, motivation.
2. Organizational factors: leadership style, Human Resource Management practices, job resources.
3. Work environment factors: toxic workplace environment, workplace spirituality, support systems.

Based on the strengths and limitations of the 22 articles, it can be concluded that:

1. Employee engagement is a complex phenomenon that requires integrated theoretical approaches, rigorous methods, and appropriate population contexts.
2. Future studies should pay attention to sampling quality, mediation and moderation testing, and the selection of theories that better explain psychological mechanisms.
3. Researchers and Human Resource Management practitioners should consider the combination of personal, organizational, and work culture factors in designing effective interventions to enhance employee engagement.

RQ4: What factors are recommended for further research?

Based on the discussion of RQ1 and RQ2, variables that have been less frequently examined include communication, job resources, individual spirituality, individual perception, trait engagement, and person organization fit. These variables may serve as reference variables for future research. Future research may also focus on the healthcare sector, which has received limited attention. In addition, the MSME sector can be examined further, particularly with a focus on MSME employees in Indonesia. To obtain representative samples, sampling techniques should be aligned with research objectives, population characteristics, and available resources.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the Systematic Literature Review of 24 selected articles from the period 2020 to 2025, it can be concluded that employee engagement is a multidimensional construct influenced by a combination of individual, organizational, and work environment factors. Organizational factors such as leadership style, Human Resource Management practices, organizational support, and quality of work life consistently show a significant effect on the level of employee engagement. In addition, work environment conditions, including the presence of toxic workplace environment and workplace spirituality, also play a role in shaping the dynamics of employee engagement across various sectors. In terms of context, research on employee engagement is still dominated by the corporate, manufacturing, and service sectors, while studies in the MSME sector, particularly in Indonesia, remain very limited. The implication is that future research is recommended to expand the population context for example the healthcare sector and MSMEs in Indonesia, examine variables that have been less frequently studied such as communication, job resources, toxic workplace environment, trait engagement, person organization fit, and individual perception factors, and use more integrated theoretical frameworks with stronger methodological designs. Thus, future findings are expected to provide more comprehensive theoretical contributions as well as practical recommendations applicable to the development of policies and interventions aimed at enhancing employee engagement in the workplace.

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